

A Critique of Re-Thinking On Science and Society for The Sustainable Future

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Abstract- The paper entitled A Critique of re-thinking on Science and Society for sustainable future is an attempt to discover how science and society sustain the future. It also analyzes the nature and functions of science both in the primitive and civilized society. There is an insight into the origin and evolution of science and society and how it can become scientific society and how sustainability is connected and interwoven with them and it follows the strength of the bright future with the coordination of science. The paper also gives vivid descriptions and arguments with analyses of science and society. The paper finally tries to define how objective entity blends with subjective entity in sustaining the future.

Keywords- Science, Society, Sustainability, development, objectivity, subjectivity, digital, device, economic, evolution, culture, harmony, logic, insight, exchange, needs, wants, progress, and objective correlativeness.

I. Introduction

The paper begins with what is science? Evolution of science, why science? Nature and functions of science, who invented the science? Relevance of science, various forms of science and how a society can be developed and sustained with its impact on man for his development and its contributions for future society. Is science become a value which passes through generations. Science is a systematic study of a body of knowledge. Any knowledge which is acquired by man is to be systematic. What is systematic? the systematic involves objective based knowledge. It can be explained by logical reason and understood without confusion.

There is an experimental method used to illustrate the facts. Usually facts can be visible and diagnosable. Science is existed when man began to ask questions to accept the facts which he came across in the journey of his primitive life. He enquires when he is not comfortable with any kind of acquired knowledge. When the knowledge is faithless, naturally he begins to doubts and wants to clear the doubts objectively. The sense of enquiry enables to discover the facts and rejects false. It is what Kuvempu the national poet interprets as rationality and logical thinking. When man thinks and accepts the new ideas, the word science might be existed.

Is man always doubts and enquires and accepts the knowledge? No. not always. Then why science? Is it useful to man to lead the life? Is it a basic need for a man? Naturally there is a curiosity and crazy in man which leads him to test and accept the knowledge when it is useful to him progressively. The difficult tasks in his life could be come easy when he when he used scientific knowledge. The knowledge which is obtained logically and scientifically is known as scientific knowledge. The transformation of man from primitive man to modern man is a long scientific journey.

With the developments in technologies and by the inventions in science man begins to lead comfortable life by using scientific equipment's and makes his life easy. He begins to use machines to lessen his physical burden and gradually he depends on the machines. His needs become wants with the developments. His life style, accommodation, food habits, mannerism, dress code and transportation and improvement in health and avoids deaths. Thus, science changes his social life and his status. He begins to earn more easily and his income increases. Poverty in life changes. There is lot of changes taken place in the life of man and he becomes modern man.

Origin of society is taken place when the stone age man lived together with his fellow beings and settled on the bank of rivers and his food and shelter changes, begins agriculture as a profession, irrigation project, power, machines and industries, manufacturing, products, goods and services and customer and consumer, market, banking, profit and loss, credit and debit, exchange of money and transaction of currency and digital transaction of currency, digital account and balance. Thus economic status of man changes. Henceforth naturally his social status and cultural diversity and language development have been rapidly uplifts the man to the higher rank in socio-economic status. All these privileges become milestone for his success.

On the other hand, there is big question before us is, how society can be sustained by the science today. To understand this, we do look into the term sustainability. George P Mitchell is widely recognized as the father of the expression sustainability for his role in popularizing the concept of sustainable development. He championed the idea of balancing economic growth with ecological well-being. Sustainable development is an approach to the growth and human development that aims to meet the needs of the present life without compromising.

The term is associated with economic growth and connected with social development. Social status can be changed with economic growth. It is advised to keep the ecofriendly development but it is not literally observed.

It is the need of the hour to re-think of sustainable society and its developments. And we have to redefine science and society. There was an unstructured society which was sustained without any typical agencies like today. Because every activity in any digital society depends on smart devices. It is an electronic connectivity between man the world today. The knowledge of digital device and its application decides the progress of man in the present society. It becomes inevitable for modern man to furnish and begin his regular natural activities. With the support of digital sciences and tools he can sustain his society. E- device plays a significant and remarkable role in the life today's man.

Natural science is set back and kept aside today just to keep sustainable development of man in society. Because no corporate society can nor run/ progress without digital developments. In the world of digital science man loses all his natural relationships and development and natural sustainability as in the traditional society. Development of society is based on advanced economic resources, technological devices, advanced social institutions, high standard of living, string social structure,

strong cultural development and high quality of life with morality and humanity. It also involves fostering positive individual values, promoting community engagements, and implementing sustainable policies by the government.

It can be achieved through encouraging empathy and mutual respect, contributing to the community with skilled labors, supporting infrastructure and awareness to pay taxes for the government. In the light of the above said developments science should stand systematically in all progressive activities to sustain the society for the future. But today new scientific inventions are being used in negative means as man is the most self-centered breeding and not being today. It is unfortunate to promote scientific tools for unscientific thoughts. Hence, science should work in the vision of strengthening ideal sustainable society for the future. To meet this end digital man today to be educated systematically and unfolds his knowledge for humanity development.

However, life today can't escape from electronic and sensor impact. Just a tool can pass the sustainable elements for future generations. Today science and society are going hand in hand but not hand in bond. It is a tragedy that man cannot live without scientific products and he himself becomes just a product. The very term sustainability is a process but it becomes a product.

When science becomes social, then naturally society is scientifically sustained for future. Therefore, it called as social science which supports healthy and harmonious society for future. Finally, the paper hopes to sustain eco-friendly science. It is theory of Eco-socio-spiritual-science which is blend of subjective and objective ideology.

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